

Design and hydrothermal synthesis of an unprecedented luminescent (7,7)-connected binodal potassium-pyrazolate coordination framework

Atanu Jana^{*a}, Pradip Kumar Sukul^b and Anamika Dhara^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : atanujanaic@gmail.com

^bPolymer Science Unit, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Kolkata-700 032, India

Manuscript received online 01 March 2014, revised 14 March 2014, accepted 23 March 2014

Abstract : A novel compound (KHL)_n [KHL = potassium 5-carboxy-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carboxylate] has been synthesized following a unique “green” methodology, which is a (7,7)-connected binodal network with {4¹⁵.6⁶} {4¹⁷.6⁴} topology of potassium-pyrazolate coordination framework with strong fluorescence behaviour.

Keywords : Potassium, pyrazolate, hydrothermal synthesis, luminescent.

Introduction

In crystal engineering, the researchers over the past three decades have engineered the construction of numerous supramolecular assemblies by predicting and controlling the organization of molecular building blocks in the solid state. The rational design and construction of metal organic frameworks (MOFs) are promising area of current research in both chemistry and materials science because of their versatile applications in catalysis, separation, gas storage, molecular recognition and nonlinear optics as well as their aesthetical architectures and elegant framework topologies¹⁻⁷. Most of the MOFs were formed by the transition metals but the MOFs formed by only alkali metals were not well explored due to the common notion that owing to the large size and small charge, alkali metals are less prone to form MOFs⁸⁻¹¹. Recently, the flexural mode aromatic dicarboxylic acid is used as the bridging ligands owing to its specific coordinational directivity, appropriate flexibility and easy of modification¹²⁻¹⁵, and can also be used for constructing different types of MOFs. KHL is a less angle flexural mode aromatic dicarboxylic acid and has a great impact on the supramolecular architecture of MOFs which take on the characteristic configuration, such as helix and folding, through hydrogen-bonding and π - π stacking interactions^{16,17}. The MOF **1** crystallized from water was inex-

pensive and importantly, “green” in the sense that it was synthesized from an acid salt [potassium 5-carboxy-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carboxylate] of potassium without using any other chemicals except water as an innocent solvent. The above mentioned procedure for preparation of MOF **1** is unique and used first time in our laboratory.

A compound of similar composition was reported by An *et al.*¹⁸. The reported compound has similar empirical formula : C₅H₃KN₂O₄, space group : P2(1)/c and crystal system : monoclinic to that of MOF **1** prepared by us. They have used 3,5-pyrazoledicarboxylic acid, Zn(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, KSCN and co-solvent H₂O-MeOH to prepare their complex but we have used simply potassium 5-carboxy-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carboxylate and H₂O. Additionally, the mode of attachment of the ligand and the topology of MOF **1** are completely different from the reported one. The MOF **1** possesses (7,7)-connected binodal network with {4¹⁵.6⁶} {4¹⁷.6⁴} topology which is also uncommon for potassium MOFs.

Herein, we report the synthesis, structure, and photoluminescence studies of **1** using the ligand potassium 5-carboxy-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carboxylate¹⁹ (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Materials and physical methods :

All chemicals were of reagent grade, purchased from

Scheme 1. Preparation of complex **1** by hydrothermal method.

commercial sources and used without further purification. Acetyl acetone and hydrazine were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All other solvents were spectroscopic grade. Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) of the ligand and the metal complexes were determined with a Perkin-Elmer CHN analyzer 2400 at the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata. The mass spectrum of the ligand was done at Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, Kolkata with a JEOLJMS-AX 500 mass spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr pellet, 100–4000 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer. Fluorescence studies of solid samples, prepared in a quartz plate as a film, were carried out with Horiba Jobin Yvon Fluoromax 3 instrument at excited wavelength 280 nm for ligand and 350 nm for complex **1**. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was done with a TA thermal analysis system at heating rate 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under N_2 environment. Eyla convection oven model no. NDO-451SD has been used to prepare **1**.

Synthesis of the ligand (KHL) :

The ligand KHL [potassium 5-carboxy-1H-pyrazole-3-carboxylate] was synthesized by following the usual reported method¹⁹.

Syntheses of complex (KHL)_n :

The ligand [potassium 5-carboxy-1H-pyrazole-3-carboxylate] (1.94 g, 10 mmol) suspension in 15 mL water was taken in 25 mL teflon lined autoclave. The vessel was sealed and heated to 170 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 72 h. Then the solution was cooled to the room temperature producing to X-ray quality white crystals of **1** (Yield : 75%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_3\text{KN}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 30.93; H, 1.56; K, 20.13; N, 14.43. Found : C, 30.91; H, 1.54; K, 20.16; N, 14.41.

X-Ray crystallography study :

Selected crystal data for all complex **1** is given in Table 1 and selected metrical parameters of the com-

Table 1. Crystallographic data of **1**

Compound	1
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_3\text{KN}_2\text{O}_4$
Formula weight	194.19
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Wavelength (\AA)	0.71069
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P2(1)/c
Unit cell dimensions :	
<i>a</i> (\AA)	8.330(5)
<i>b</i> (\AA)	11.273(5)
<i>c</i> (\AA)	7.272(5)
α ($^\circ$)	90.000(5)
β ($^\circ$)	91.757(5)
γ ($^\circ$)	90.000(5)
Volume (\AA^3)	682.5(7)
<i>z</i>	4
Density _{cal} (mg m^{-3})	1.890
Absorption coefficient (mm^{-1})	0.749
<i>F</i> (000)	392
θ Range ($^\circ$) for data collection	4.1 to 25.0
Index ranges	$-9 \leq h \leq 8$ $-13 \leq k \leq 13$ $8 \leq l \leq 8$
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.823
Completeness to theta	0.989
Independent reflections [R_{int}]	1189 [0.070]
Refinement method	Full-matrix least squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	1189/1/113
Reflections collected	5961
Final <i>R</i> indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.1103$, $wR_2 = 0.1329$
Largest difference peak and hole ($\text{e}\text{\AA}^{-3}$)	-0.67 and 1.47

plexes are given in Table 2. For complex **1** data collections were made using Bruker SMART APEX II CCD

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) data for **1**

Selected bonds	Value (Å)	Selected angles	(°)
K1-O4	2.664(4)	O2_b-K1-O4	77.76(12)
K1-O2_b	2.920(4)	O1_d-K1-O4	108.95(13)
K1-O1_d	2.670(4)	O3_f-K1-O4	126.37(13)
K1-O3_f	3.016(4)	O2_g-K1-O4	160.31(13)
K1-O2_g	2.878(4)	O3_i-K1-O4	95.82(14)
K1-O3_i	2.983(5)	O1_k-K1-O4	65.05(12)
K1-O1_k	2.825(4)	O1_d-K1-O2_b	154.38(11)
O1-C1	1.230(6)	O2_b-K1-O3_f	64.79(11)
O2-C1	1.284(6)	O2_b-K1-O2_g	99.84(10)
		O2_b-K1-O3_i	67.46(10)
		O1_k-K1-O2_b	82.04(10)
		O1_d-K1-O3_f	93.03(12)
		O1_d-K1-O2_g	81.78(11)
		O1_d-K1-O3_i	133.72(12)
		O1_d-K1-O1_k	78.96(11)
		O2_g-K1-O3_f	67.54(11)
		O3_f-K1-O3_i	103.03(11)
		O1_k-K1-O3_f	72.65(11)
		O2_g-K1-O3_i	65.71(11)
		O1_k-K1-O2_g	134.39(11)
		O1_k-K1-O3_i	147.22(12)
		K1_c-O1-C1	121.7(3)
		K1_c-O1-K1_h	101.07(12)
		K1_a-O2-K1_g	80.16(9)
		K1_e-O3-K1_j	76.97(9)

area detector equipped with graphite monochromated Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71069$ Å) source in ϕ and ω scan mode at 296 K. Cell parameters refinement and data reduction for all complexes were carried out using the Bruker SMART²⁰ and Bruker SAINT softwares. The structure **1** were solved by conventional direct methods and refined by full-matrix least square methods using F^2 data. SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs²¹ were used for structure of all the complexes solution and refinement respectively. For all complexes non hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically till the convergence is attained.

Results and discussion

Structural description of complex **1** :

A single-crystal X-ray diffraction study of **1** reveals an infinite assembly consisting of seven coordinate K centres and bridging pyrazole dicarboxylate groups. **1** crystallizes in the monoclinic space group P21/c. The asym-

metric unit consists of one K(I) center and one monodeprotonated pyrazole dicarboxylic acid. The K(I) cation is coordinated by seven oxygen atoms from seven different ligands and one nitrogen atom forming a distorted dodecahedral geometry (Fig. 1a). All the K–O bond lengths vary considerably from 2.666(4) Å to 3.015(4) Å and K–N bond distance is 3.300(4) Å. Each monodeprotonated pyrazole dicarboxylate ligand adopts the unusual $\mu_7, \eta^2 : \eta^2 : \eta^2 : \eta^1 : \eta^1$ coordination mode that binds to seven K(I) cation through seven oxygen atoms from three bidentate oxygen, one hydroxyl from carboxylic groups and one nitrogen atom to construct two-dimensional (2D) wavy sheet around bc plane (Fig. 1b). 3D view along a-axis is shown in Fig. 1c. Topological analysis indicates that it is a complicated binodal (7,7)-connected net with a point symbol of $\{4^{15}.6^6\}\{4^{17}.6^4\}$ (Fig. 1d). The distances between the two pyrazole rings and two potassium ions (K1) are 6.125 Å and 7.573 Å. One pyrazole carboxylate ligand moiety attached to eight K atom.

Emission behavior :

We investigated the photoluminescence properties of **1** in the solid state at room temperature (Fig. 2). To understand the nature of these emission bands, we also examined the luminescent properties of the free ligand KHL. The ligand displayed luminescence with an emission maximum at 411 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 280$ nm), which is attributed to the π^* to n transition²². The fluorescent emission bands of **1** are $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 479$ nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 350$ nm). For **1**, the emission of 479 nm experienced a large bathochromic shift of 68 nm relative to that of the ligand. The fluorescence intensity of the complex is dramatically enhanced compared to that of the ligand. It may be attributed to the high-dimensional structure and π - π stacking interactions, which strengthen the rigidity of the framework and lower the loss of energy²³. The distance between the two pyrazole moieties in **1** is 3.639 Å which is suitable for flow of electrons throughout the 3-dimensional MOF and consequently the enhancement of fluorescence intensity occurs. The results indicate that the structure of the complex **1** has subtle but significant influences on the photoluminescent intensities.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) :

To estimate the stability of the MOF **1**, thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were carried out. Result of the

Fig. 1. (a) Dodecahedron geometry of K coordinated by seven oxygen atom from seven different L and one nitrogen atom from one L. (b) K^+ ion and carboxylate bridged 2D sheet formed along bc-plane in K. (c) 3D view along c-axis in K. (d) Topological view of (7,7)-connected binodal net in K. Point symbol $\{4^{15}.6^6\}\{4^{17}.6^4\}$.

Fig. 2. The solid state fluorescence spectra of ligand (a) and complex **1** (b) at ambient temperature. Excitation wavelength for ligand and complex **1**, $\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm and 350 nm respectively, slit width used 2/2 nm.

TGA curve shows that **1** possesses considerable thermal stability (Fig. S1), the curve appear as straight line up to 245 °C, which indicates that **1** is extremely stable up to

Fig. S1. Thermogravimetric analysis curve of **1** in air.

245 °C or so. Beyond this temperature, the organic components begin to decompose and the framework finally collapses. Intriguingly, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of **1** showed this material to have a significantly smaller solvent capacity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have successfully synthesized a (7,7)-connected luminescent binodal potassium-pyrazolate MOF by self-assembly of a monopotassium salt of pyrazole dicarboxylic acid in water under suitable hydrothermal conditions following green methodology. Each monodeprotonated pyrazole dicarboxylate ligand adopts an unusual μ_7 coordination mode to produce the interpenetrating layers of **1**. The substantial π - π stacking interactions in **1** strengthen the rigidity of the framework causing chelation enhanced fluorescence of the complex compared to that of the ligand.

Acknowledgements

X-Ray crystallography was performed at the DST funded National Single Crystal Diffractometer facility at the Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta.

Supplementary data

CCDC 871690 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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